

D5.2

EMPOWER

deliverables

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The following report, produced by Work Package 5, documents “the exchange of experiences, expectations, and concerns as expressed by Work Package researchers and stakeholders during the first auditing session” (Empower, 2021) of the Empower Project

Description

Executive summary

Furthermore, it aims to provide other consortium members with ethical guidance by presenting an “improved framework specification” (Empower, 2021) developed via the methods outlined in deliverable 5.1. More specifically, it explains how Work Package 5 implemented the “ethical cycle” (van de Poel & Royakkers, 2011) to identify and address concerns that became evident between Spring 2023 and Spring 2024. The method employed enabled Work Package 5 to gather insights from other Work Packages and, subsequently, adapt its ethical framework. As such, the findings presented in this report were produced via a collaborative effort led by Work Package 5, designed to help the Empower Project enrich its methods through ethical reflection and, ultimately, meet its core objectives.

Date	Version	Description	Authors
05.06.2024	1.0	First Draft of the conceptual development protocol and subsequent reviews after comments from EB and EthB	Pim Haselager, Thomasin Coggins

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1. Introduction

The report includes insights and recommendation pertaining to specific Work Packages and the Empower Project in general. Nonetheless, we believe that all Work Packages will benefit from reading the report in its entirety, as it provides an overview of Work Package 5's ongoing efforts to develop a holistic framework that Empower Project members can collectively employ. To date, the recommendations outlined in this report have yet to be fully implemented largely because Work Package 5 developed them after the Empower Project's pilot study. Many of these recommendations build on the ethical practices already employed by other Work Packages, therefore consortium members may implement them by adapting their current research methods without further support from Work Package 5. Whereas others amount to novel suggestions that may require Work Package 5 to actively collaborate with other Work Packages to implement (e.g., via consultations, research design reviews, and the creation of addendums to proposed studies). We clarify in the recommendations section of this report how other consortium members can use Work Package 5's suggestions with or without our direct involvement at relevant stages during the project's planned research.

The report proceeds as follows. In section 2, we outline the methods used to produce this report and the "improved framework specifications" (Empower, 2021). In section 3, we present new ethical insights concerning how to empower relevant stakeholders. In sections 4, we provide improved recommendations developed between December 2023 to March 2024. And in section 5, we highlight the limitations of this report and outline the future directions of our research.

2. Methods

As specified in Deliverable 5.1, Work Package 5 uses the "ethical cycle" method, as described by numerous philosophers of technology (van de Poel & Royakkers, 2012).

Additionally, we have drawn from other comparable methods, when necessary, for instance, Value Sensitive Design, Design Justice, and Design for Values (Friedman et al., 2002; van den Hoven, 2007; Kroes & van de Poel, 2015; Costanza-Chock, 2020). These methods collectively propose that ethicists working in interdisciplinary projects created to develop technology for specific stakeholders should firstly consult the literature concerning said stakeholders' needs to identify pertinent ethical concerns, with the aim of identifying the central concepts used in research in the field of technological applications. Afterwards, they should consult other project members and, ideally, as many relevant stakeholders as possible to communicate their findings and test their applicability. Such consultations should lead to another round of literature research that employs feedback from the external parties mentioned earlier to generate improved ethical insights and recommendations. Because this method focuses on communicating then updating ethical insights during the development of a given technology, it is well-suited for the Empower Project's needs and enables us to continuously reflect on our work's relevance for other Work Packages and help them develop technologies tailored to stakeholders' needs.

Proponents of the "ethical cycle", and the other methods mentioned above, generally maintain that practitioners should gather first-hand, qualitative data from stakeholders. Work Package 5 could not pursue this aim directly due to the inaccessibility of suitable informants (e.g., teachers, parents, and children participating in the Empower Project) because of language barriers (neither author of this document speaks Romanian or Portuguese, i.e., potential informants' native and likely only language). As such, we have instead consulted sociological accounts of how disabled people, especially from the neurodiverse community, view and respond to scientific research concerning their disabilities (Hacking, 2000; Pearson & Rose, 2023; Tan, 2024) and gathered insights from other members of the consortium concerning their experiences working in this area. Therefore, we have addressed this limitation to the best of our abilities by synthesizing information from secondary sources that directly and indirectly represent relevant stakeholders' views and needs concerning the technologies developed by the Empower

Project. Additionally, we created this report after consulting members of other Work Packages to discern their impressions of Deliverable 5.1, discuss the applicability of our earlier research, and identify ethical concerns they encountered within their work. The appendices of Deliverable 5.1. includes summaries of these consultation sessions.

3. Definition of Empowerment

In Deliverable 5.1, we stated that we will conduct an ongoing conceptual analysis of the term “empowerment”. We proposed this research line for two reasons. Firstly, the philosophical, political, and sociological literature on empowerment contains various, often conflicting accounts of what this term represents. Secondly, the Empower Project aims to empower its key stakeholders via technological interventions and therefore should establish how we can determine that this has occurred. Additionally, we highlighted that “self-esteem” may serve as a suitable core value for analyzing neurodiverse children’s empowerment because it reflects one’s perceptions of oneself. We have since worked towards the aims mentioned above via in-depth literature reviews of the main concepts (empowerment, self-determination, emotion regulation, and self-esteem) and developed the recommendations presented in this report partly in response. Indeed, we maintain that paying attention to how the Empower Project’s research effects neurodiverse participants’ self-esteem may help us understand whether said research does, indeed, empower them for the following reasons.

The literature on self-esteem contends that this concept reflects an individual’s evaluation of themselves that they develop chiefly by comparing themselves to their peers (Rosenberg, 1965; Honneth, 1996). It represents how one judges what one believes to know about oneself – which is often called “self-concept” in the sociologically literature (Bong & Skaalvik, 2003). For instance, “I am good at mathematics” is a descriptive statement that represents an individual’s assumedly true belief that they have a specific competency, thus is tied to their self-concept. Whereas “I am proud that I am good at

mathematics” demonstrates that an individual appreciates said competency. Such judgements affect one’s normative assessment of oneself (self-esteem) as they provide reasons to evaluate oneself positively or negatively. Some examples drawn from education will help illustrate the meaning of self-esteem and its ethical import for the Empower Project. Children with high self-esteem will see themselves as “good enough” when asked to compare their ability to complete schoolwork to their classmates’ (Rosenberg, 2015). Rather than feeling exceptional or incapable, they recognize that they share similar competences to their average peer and meet culturally determined standards that demonstrate this (e.g., obtain decent grades or do not attract negative attention from their teachers).

Due to various social and psychological factors, neurodiverse people often have more difficulty maintaining high self-esteem than their neurotypical peers (Lee, Patal, & Scior, 2023; Strang et al. 2024). Indeed, children diagnosed with autism, ADHD, and other neurodevelopment conditions often receive specialized treatment within educational settings to address symptomatic behaviors that prevent them from performing tasks in a manner comparable to neurotypical students (Pellicano & den Houting, 2022). Being differentiated in this way may cause them to feel less competent than other children of the same age group, thus having a negative effect on their self-esteem.

Furthermore, this may lead to internalized stigmatization and, possibly, the development of co-morbid mental illnesses (Strang et al., 2024). If other school children know that students with neurodevelopment conditions need specialized help, they may tease or bully them for being abnormal. When left unaddressed, such stigmatization can cause victims to internalize others’ evaluations of their presumed deficits and develop negative attitudes towards themselves, thus decreasing their self-esteem. Research suggests that low self-esteem may predict or partially cause various mental illnesses such as depression and generalized anxiety disorder (Rosenberg, 2015; Silverstone & Salsali, 2003; Sowislo & Orth, 2013; Strang et al. 2024). Therefore, ensuring that neurodiverse children maintain high self-

esteem may benefit their overall health and help them succeed during and after their school years. An important question for the Empower project is therefore how the use of AI might affect, and potentially improve, children's self-esteem.

Some philosophers also maintain that high self-esteem ensures that individuals know they deserve fair treatment from their peers, institutions, and the government (Rawls, 1971; Honneth, 1992). When people with high self-esteem experience discrimination or injustices, they tend to understand that another party has disrespected them (Honneth, 1992). In contrast, individuals with low self-esteem may fail to recognize this and believe they possess traits that merit such reactions (e.g., they have insufficiencies or abnormalities that others rightly dislike). Considering that neurodiverse people often encounter oppression because they possess characteristics many people and institutions consider deficits, if they have low self-esteem, they may see themselves as undeserving of better treatment. Negative self-attitudes of this kind may cause an affected individual to neglect or abandon important goals at school or work, because they believe that success is beyond the capabilities of someone like them (Rosenberg, 2015; Honneth, 1992; Lee, Patel, & Scior 2023).

As the Empower Project aims to help neurodiverse students succeed at school and, ultimately, find meaningful employment, we contend that the project would benefit from incorporating in its research the significant role self-esteem plays in these contexts. Succeeding at school, for instance, requires students to believe that they can and deserve to do so. Such attitudes reflect high self-esteem. Therefore, establishing means to ensure students cultivate them may help the Empower Project meet its core objectives more effectively. Although self-esteem may not equate precisely to empowerment, having a positive attitude towards oneself enables individuals to (potentially) remain mentally well, know they deserve fair treatment, and pursue long-term goals. The rest of this deliverable presents ethical insights and recommendations tailored around the ideas outlined above.

4. Recommendations

In Deliverable 5.1, we outlined a preliminary ethical framework which centered around three major themes, labelled *Individualization of Disability*, *Knowledge Consolidation*, and *Data Choices*. We have since reviewed and revised the work completed in Deliverable 5.1 via the methods outlined in section 2 of this report. Moreover, we have developed a selection of actionable recommendations designed to (partially) address some of the concerns raised in Deliverable 5.1.

4.1 INDIVIDUALIZATION OF DISABILITY

4.1.1 Introduction

As stated in Deliverable 5.1, disabled people often face hardships because their psychological and social environments do not accommodate their impairment(s) (Oliver, 1990). This holds true for neurodiverse people. As such, we recommended that the Empower Project pay attention to how its research may place its primary research participants, namely neurodiverse children, in contexts that cause them avoidable stress or discomfort. We have identified two concerns related to this theme and provide recommendations to address them below.

4.1.2 Interview Settings

Concern

Numerous scholars working in participatory research concerning neurodiverse children have highlighted that conducting scientifically and ethically-sound interviews, focus groups, and other qualitative empirical studies with this group poses various interrelated challenges (Teachman & Gibson, 2012; Pelicano & Houting, 2022). Most notably, neurodiverse children may become distracted or distressed by noises, smells, or lights due

to their (possible) sensory hypersensitivities – stimuli which neurotypical researchers might not notice or consider bothersome (Pelicano & Houting, 2022). Additionally, participants may feel uncomfortable talking in unfamiliar settings such as universities or offices, especially when they do not know the researchers conducting said interviews (et cetera) (Fletcher-Watson et al., 2019; Pelicano & den Houting, 2022). This may cause participants to feel overwhelmed and potentially have trouble answering questions. Furthermore, neurodiverse children with speech and language impairments who use alternative or augmented communication (e.g., sign-language, paper-based systems, or technologies designed for these purposes) will likely feel especially distressed, or indeed, be unable to adequately communicate, if they cannot rely on these communication strategies during interactions with researchers. Even though participants who experiences such distractions or communicative obstacles may provide seemingly useable responses, their answers may include information that does not accurately reflect their experiences due to the confounding influence of stress or discomfort.

Recommendations

According to the literature cited above, neurodiverse children provide better responses to questions when invited to participate in qualitative research in settings they have influence over and find comfortable. For instance, several researchers have suggested that it is best to conduct such research inside children's family homes, as participants often feel safer and able to control (possible) distractions in these locations (Fletcher-Watson et al., 2019; Pelicano & den Houting, 2022). If this is not possible, researchers could instead spend time before interviews, et cetera, discussing with participants how they feel about their surroundings to determine whether said locations include distracting stimuli (Cocks, 2006; Scott-Barrett, Cebula, & Florian, 2019). Afterwards, researchers could attempt to adjust an interview setting to accommodate participants' sensory needs (e.g., dim lights or close curtains) or arrange to conduct their research somewhere the participants find agreeable. Additionally, ensuring that children who rely on alternative and augmented

communication can (and know that they can) use these strategies during interactions will almost certainly provide them with a sense of control they may otherwise lack. Of course, limited time or financial constraints may negatively affect the possibility to provide such circumstances. In such cases, it might be useful to take note of, and analyze data for, possible signs of negative effects of research or testing conditions.

Implementation

Work Package 5 can provide more concrete suggestions concerning how to implement this recommendation prior to the next round of qualitative research conducted with participants. These suggestions will translate the findings documented in the literature cited in the sub-section above (among other sources) into actionable insights which other Work Packages may adapt into their research – most notably Work Package 2. This task will likely require further consultation with other consortium members to assess the feasibility of said recommendations.

4.1.3 Wearable Technologies

Concern

Neurodiverse children participating in the Empower Project's research will interact with technologies that include wearable devices. These devices gather data concerning the child's heart rate and eye movements to help researchers from Work Package 4 improve their algorithms. However, children (particularly neurodiverse ones) may find wearing these devices cumbersome, intrusive, or distracting (Spiel et al., 2019). Moreover, neurodiverse children generally experience considerably more behavioral and physiological monitoring than their neurotypical peers, which they usually have little control over (Spiel, 2019; Pelicano & den Houting, 2022; Pearson & Rose, 2023; Tan, 2024). For instance, they typically interact with medical professionals and educational specialists considerably more often than neurotypical children. Moreover, they usually cannot opt-in

or out of such measurement efforts as their parental guardians decide this for them. This may lead to neurodiverse children suffering from a loss of privacy, autonomy, and agency – especially when they have their data collected against their wishes.

Recommendations

Although it will decrease the useable data collected during gaming sessions, allowing participants to autonomously decide whether they will undergo biometric monitoring mediated via wearables will mitigate the concerns raised. For instance, researchers could explain to them before gaming sessions that they may remove the wearables whenever they want. Or choose not to wear them at all. Additionally, researchers may clarify to participants that these devices help improve the games being designed by the Empower Project rather than survey their individual behavior. These measures would provide participants with a sense of control they may otherwise lack and, ideally, ensure that they know they deserve the same expectations of privacy as their neurotypical peers. Here too, taking explicit note of potential ways in which data collection might affect neurodiverse children is important.

Implementation

This recommendation may be implemented without Work Package 5's direct involvement as it chiefly requires consortium members who have direct contact with research participants to explain to them why the data collected by the wearables are important and that they may remove them. Nonetheless, Work Package 5 can provide further support if necessary (e.g., by developing written research protocol for relevant consortium members – most notably Work Package 2). Additionally, further discussions with Work Package 4 are potentially required to assess the feasibility of collecting data without the usage of wearable devices.

4.2 PARTICIPATION

4.2.1 Knowledge Consolidation

As stated in Deliverable 5.1, neurodiverse people have historically had little influence over how the scientific community studied them despite having expert knowledge of their experiences (Fletcher-Watson, et al., 2017; Pelicano & Den Houing, 2022; Tan, 2024). Over the past few decades, philosophers of science have recommended that scientists consult members of marginalized groups they wish to study to improve the ethical and scientific validity of their research (Harding, 2015; Hill Collins & Bilge, 2016; D'Ignazio & Klein, 2020). As such, we recommended the Empower Project consolidate knowledge created by neurodiverse people into its research to simultaneously avoid repeating this omission and generate data and methods that more adequately represents its primary research participants' perspectives (neurodiverse children). We have identified two concerns related to this theme and provide recommendations to address them below.

4.2.2 Participatory Research

Concern

The Empower Project uses participatory research to design and improve the games it is developing. So far, it has consulted teachers, neurodiversity experts, and Autism Europe via various means (e.g., focus groups, questionnaires, and interviews). It also allows neurodiverse children to influence the games' design via feedback collected by teachers. However, research participants do not directly influence the Empower Project's research design, which, of course, is typical for research projects in general, but in this context also chiefly because the participants are children. Nonetheless, the ethical literature on participatory research concerning neurodiverse people (including children) recommends that researchers gather and respond to feedback from neurodiverse participants as thoroughly as possible (e.g., by listening to their views on the research questions posed,

data collection methods, and the interpretation of results) (Cocks & Cockram, 1995; Stalker, 2010; Fletcher-Wilson et al., 2019). Ideally, this enables research participants to contribute to scientific discourse that directly affects them (Cocks & Cockram, 1995; Stalker, 1998; Fletcher-Wilson et al., 2019). Considering that the Empower Project's neurodiverse participants are young and may experience difficulties in providing comprehensive scientific advice, ensuring that they contribute to the project as outlined above poses challenges.

Recommendations

Although young children usually do not have the fully developed communication and reasoning skills needed to provide feedback on studies' research designs, researchers can translate their stated preferences into actionable insights (Stalker 1998; Cocks, 2006; Cridland et al., 2015). For instance, researchers working with the Empower Project could ask participants to discuss how they feel about being studied before and after gaming sessions, et cetera (e.g., whether they understand why they are playing a game, agree that it benefits them, or consent to data collection) (Scott-Barret, Cebula, & Florian, 2019). Moreover, many neurodiverse children with speech and language impairments rely on alternative or augmented communication strategies during interactions. Ensuring that research participants can use these strategies and have access to their preferred aids during interactions with researchers will allow them to express their opinions more comprehensively.

Additionally, researchers have developed methods to represent neurodiverse people's experiences more accurately in their qualitative research when they cannot rely on direct participant feedback (Teachman & Gibson, 2013; Cridland et al., 2015; Strang, et al., 2018). Empower researchers could, for instance, ask neurodiverse adults - who have completed primary education in the European Union – to interpret participants' responses to the questionnaires completed during gaming sessions and check whether they contain

information that a neurotypical person may overlook. Such measures would potentially require arranging another round of focus group studies but may ensure that the Empower Projects' results reflect its participants' experiences more rigorously.

Implementation

Work Package 5 can provide more concrete suggestions concerning how to implement this recommendation prior to the next round of research conducted with research participants. These suggestions will translate the findings documented in the literature cited in the subsection above (among other sources) into actionable insights which other Work Packages may adapt into their research – most notably Work Package 2. This task will likely require further consultation with other consortium members to assess the feasibility of said recommendations.

4.2.3 Post-Study Participant Dissatisfaction

Concern

Reporting shows that people who participate in scientific studies focusing on neurodiversity often feel disappointed or frustrated after a project's completion when it is unclear how (or if) the results produced benefit them or their community (Fletcher-Watson, et al., 2019; Pelicano & den Houting, 2022). Furthermore, studies of this kind have historically skewed towards identifying the causes and symptoms of conditions such as autism or ADHD rather than aiming to improve participants' material and social circumstances (e.g., via advocacy or policy recommendations designed to ensure appropriate care) (Pelicano & den Houting, 2022). As such, sociological research suggests that some neurodiverse people and their caregivers believe the scientific community does not care about their needs and instead wishes to study them for their own benefit (e.g., to further their scientific reputation or achieve funding goals) (Pelicano & den Houting, 2024; Tan, 2024). Thus, asking participants to share their knowledge and experiences may make

them feel ignored or disrespected in the long run if they do not receive updates concerning how their participation helped people like them after a study's conclusion.

Recommendation

Considering that the Empower Project explicitly aims to develop technology that improves neurodiverse children's access to education, it will, ideally, positively impact its participants' lives and the neurodiverse community, in general. Nonetheless, it does involve methods that, when left unexplained, could make participants feel studied for the sake of research that does not directly benefit them. For instance, one could interpret the data collected by wearables during gaming sessions as geared towards diagnosis rather than improving educational tools for neurodiverse children, as these devices track behaviors considered symptomatic of autism and ADHD. Considering that research suggests that many neurodiverse people and their caregivers feel as though scientific studies concerning them unduly place diagnosis above care, explaining to participants that this is not the case may decrease the likelihood that they will become dissatisfied after the Empower Project's conclusion. Moreover, the Empower Project will conclude within 2 years, and it would be important to develop means to update participants afterwards about the influence their participation had on later social or scientific endeavors focused on bettering education for neurodiverse children. As such, we recommend that the Empower Project clearly briefs participants about its goals concerning the collection of behavioral data (e.g., it is needed to improve games rather than improve diagnostic methods) and begin developing means to keep participants in the loop after the project's conclusion (e.g., a newsletter or website updates).

Implementation

If necessary, Work Package 5 can provide further support to ensure research participants know why their data are collected (e.g., by developing written research protocol for relevant consortium members – most notably Work Package 2). Additionally, Work Package

5 can help Work Package 7 to establish means to communicate the Empower Project's results to research participants to ensure they remain informed about how their participation helped advance scientific research that, ideally, will help people like them (e.g., via social media or newsletters). Both tasks will likely require further consultation with other consortium members to assess the feasibility of said recommendations.

4.3 DATA CHOICES

4.3.1 Context of legal requirements

In Deliverable 5.1., we specified that although the Empower Project observes legal requirements concerning data collection and usage within the European Union, the project may nonetheless encounter ethical issues concerning data practices that current legislation does not prohibit. For instance, by collecting data that does not adequately represent the neurodiverse community's experiences (e.g., via methods that prevent them from representing themselves) or developing practices that may inadvertently put them in harm's way. We have identified one concern related to this theme and provide recommendations to address it below.

4.3.2 The AI Act and Psychological Data

Concern

In the explanatory memorandum of the EU AI-Act, section 5.2.2. says: "The regulation follows a risk-based approach, differentiating between uses of AI that create (i) an unacceptable risk, (ii) a high risk, and (iii) low or minimal risk. The list of prohibited practices in Title II comprises all those AI systems whose use is considered unacceptable as contravening Union values, for instance by violating fundamental rights. The prohibitions cover practices that have a significant potential to manipulate persons through subliminal

techniques beyond their consciousness or exploit vulnerabilities of specific vulnerable groups such as children or persons with disabilities in order to materially distort their behavior in a manner that is likely to cause them or another person psychological or physical harm.” (European Parliament, 2024).

Preamble (16) clarifies that the aim is to forbid applications to exploit vulnerabilities of children and people due to their age, physical or mental incapacities, where there is "the intention to materially distort the behaviour of a person and in a manner that causes or is likely to cause harm to that or another person. The intention may not be presumed if the distortion of human behaviour results from factors external to the AI system which are outside of the control of the provider or the user. “. (European Parliament, 2024). Moreover, preamble (16) states explicitly that "Research for legitimate purposes in relation to such AI systems should not be stifled by the prohibition” (European Parliament, 2024).

Recommendation

Taken together this implies in our view that the use of AI technology by the Empower project is not forbidden, but that extreme care regarding the vulnerabilities of the target group is required. In principle, it seems a useful strategy to clarify in the discussion about AI usage how potential concerns about violation of fundamental rights, manipulation, exploitation, distortion of behavior, or the possibility of harm is avoided. In practice, this would require the identification of how AI usage can contribute to improving children’s self-esteem, self-determination, and emotion regulation, and actively collecting feedback on how AI usage is perceived (if at all), in combination with the recommendations provided above.

Implementation

This recommendation will require Work Package 5 to study and reflect upon both the AI Act and the Empower Project's completed and proposed research. Once Work Package 5 has completed this task, we will share further recommendations with other consortium members via consultation sessions, ideally, scheduled within the next six months.

5. Conclusion

In this report, we presented research carried out by Work Package 5 of the Empower Project over the past six months, which includes an explanation of our methods, a revised definition of empowerment via discussions on self-esteem, and a selection of new ethical concerns and recommendations we identified during the period mentioned above. In the future will continue to develop our ethical framework based on the insights and results found in this document. Moreover, we aim to more thoroughly incorporate literature and data produced by other Work Packages into our workflow, for instance, by reviewing findings and discussing their ethical relevance with the Ethical Reflection Team. Due to time limitations, we could not include a thorough review of such findings in this document. Additionally, we will endeavor to help other consortium members implement the recommendations provided in this report via consultation sessions and, ideally, direct collaborations (e.g., reviews of documents, databases, and proposed research designs).

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